

ISB, ESB, ESMAC, GCMAS, and ASB Guidelines for Open Data Sharing in the Human Movement Sciences

PART 1: ETHICAL, LEGAL, AND METADATA CONSIDERATIONS

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Abstract

Human movement sciences lack standardised data sharing practices, limiting scientific advancements in the field. These multi-society-endorsed recommendations establish foundational ethical, legal, and metadata guidelines for open sharing of kinematic data in the human movement sciences. Building on FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), the recommendations provide a practical approach for respecting participant privacy while allowing meaningful data exchange. Key considerations include distinguishing between anonymous, anonymised, and pseudonymised data, obtaining informed consent permitting broad data usage, and implementing secure technical infrastructure.

The recommendations advocate federated storage models using Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to maintain institutional control while enabling secure access across different legal jurisdictions. Clear licensing models, such as Creative Commons, are critical for ensuring proper attribution and permitted uses. Comprehensive metadata reporting should cover ethics and accessibility, experimental protocols, population characteristics, and signal processing details (including coordinate system definitions), with quality descriptors characterising data objectively rather than prescriptively. Practical recommendations emphasise adherence to international regulations, early ethics engagement, data minimisation, and the establishment of sustainable funding models. The guidelines strike a balance between rigor and practicality to promote widespread adoption in biomechanics, biomedical engineering, and human movement sciences, without creating prohibitive barriers to contribution.

With the endorsement of five international scientific societies, these recommendations provide consensus-based guidelines for open sharing of human movement data, facilitating international cross-institutional collaboration, hypothesis generation, and enhanced statistical power through aggregated datasets, all while maintaining robust privacy protection and ethical compliance.

Introduction

Over recent decades, deliberate data sharing practices have contributed to considerable scientific breakthroughs in several biomedical fields, including genomics [1-4], structural biology [5, 6], medical imaging and radiology [7, 8], and orthopaedics [9, 10]. Centralised dissemination of data has led to not only innovation, but also early interventions to address issues that would otherwise not have been identified (e.g. [10, 11]). This potential to accelerate scientific discovery and gain unprecedented insights into complex mechanisms is particularly heightened in light of recent advances in artificial intelligence that exploit large, diverse, and well-annotated datasets that no single research group could feasibly collect alone. On a personal and laboratory level, the potential benefits of sharing research data are substantial, including increased visibility and recognition, improved reputation, collaboration opportunities through enhanced networking, and even possible funding or career advancement prospects. However, in the field of human movement science, inhomogeneity in cohorts, equipment, study design, modelling, protocols, and file formats, has impeded community efforts to unite around standardised approaches for the widespread sharing of kinematic (i.e. joint rotations, translations, and their derivatives) datasets [12]. This challenge has been partly rooted in complex ethical and legal restrictions concerning the sharing of personal data, but also by the lack of dedicated computational frameworks.

Several scientific societies, such as the European Society for Movement Analysis in Adults and Children (ESMAC) [13], the Clinical Movement Analysis Society (CMAS) [14], the Italian Society of Clinical Movement Analysis (Società Italiana di Analisi del Movimento in Clinica; SIAMOC) [15], and the Society for the Analysis of Human Motor Function and its Clinical Application (Gesellschaft für die Analyse menschlicher Motorik und ihre klinische Anwendung; GAMMA) [16], have already started working towards the inception of standardised practices for the **collection** of kinematic data. International Society of Biomechanics (ISB) efforts towards establishing recommendations include an initial set of general guidelines for the definition of global and local segment reference frames in human movement [17], followed by joint-specific recommendations for the ankle, hip, and spine [18], as well as shoulder, elbow, wrist, and hand [19]. For the knee, the ISB openly endorsed the approach proposed by Grood and Suntay [20] as the preferred evaluation method. However, given the ever-present heterogeneity among datasets from different research groups, the establishment of guiding principles for data **sharing** will also play a crucial role towards achieving a level of consistency that can facilitate comparison and outcome interpretation in large population datasets.

In the context of human movement data, valuable yet isolated efforts have been initiated to pool data and make curated research resources available for community usage [21-24]. However, most research groups in the field have largely relied on the unregulated use of different publicly available non-field-specific repositories such as GitHub [25], FigShare [26], Zenodo [27], Harvard Dataverse [28], etc. to share their data and/or processing scripts. Early recommendations to underpin methods and best practices for sharing individuals' movement data have been initiated. For example, the most recent standards proposed by the ISB cover the reporting of intersegmental forces and moments [29], skin-marker-based multi-segment foot kinematics [30], as well as joint kinematics based on wearable inertial measurement technology [31]. Despite these valuable contributions, the field still lacks a unified, general framework that addresses the broader challenges of sharing human movement data across

institutions, particularly as the use of different general repositories (e.g. due to diverse server and geopolitical requirements) further perpetuates a fragmented research ecosystem. Existing ISB standards have mostly focused on specific joints or evaluation techniques, leaving a lack of guidance on how to structure, annotate, and disseminate movement datasets in a manner that builds on previous recommendations while also supporting open science practices. A recognised and standardised framework specifically for the accumulation of kinematic data is therefore currently missing. The development of such a framework could not only provide widespread access to valuable datasets collected with state-of-the-art motion capture equipment, which is available to only a few privileged laboratories. Additionally, access to aggregated datasets allows not only *a priori* idea testing, informed hypothesis generation, and evidence-driven sample size estimation, but also the enhancement of studies with small sample sizes.

1. Background & Motivation

To address the recognised hurdles of data sharing [32], several projects have aimed to identify the challenges associated with the publication of movement data and formulate foundational guidelines to promote data sharing efforts among laboratories worldwide (e.g. [33-38]). These comprehensive analyses have instituted a valuable foundation upon which a set of international guidelines can now be established. This multi-society-endorsed recommendations paper brings together researchers with expertise in biomechanics, data sharing, medical law, research ethics, and secure healthcare infrastructure development, ensuring both technical excellence and regulatory compliance across diverse global contexts. The authors hold or have held leadership positions in scientific societies and ethics committees, while having proven experience implementing Trusted Research Environments and harmonising clinical data across institutions. These recommendations therefore concatenate and build on the legal, ethical, and technical concepts explored previously, towards fostering global consensus on *open* data sharing practices and strengthening international efforts in the worldwide dissemination of human movement data. In this context, data can be considered *open* if it can be accessed, used, modified, and shared freely by users, “subject, at most, to measures that preserve provenance and openness” [39], reflecting the principle that data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” [40]. Given the breadth of relevant considerations across the field, these guidelines necessarily focus on sharing data associated with living individuals legally able to provide informed consent (rather than research contexts with unique requirements, such as data acquired from cadaveric, animal, paediatric, cognitively vulnerable, or rare disease populations), and without complex commercial situations (e.g. implant data subject to intellectual property protection). Within these boundaries, the presented framework aims to support the research community in sharing and using data responsibly, fostering a culture of openness and best practice across the field.

1.1. FAIR principles

In March 2016, a “diverse set of stakeholders – representing academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers” jointly published the FAIR principles [41]. The main aim of the FAIR principles is to serve as a set of general guidelines to ensure datasets are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Figure 1). The principles have since been endorsed by multiple intergovernmental organisations and international committees, including the Group of 20 (G20) [42], the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) [43],

and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) [44]. With the collection and publication of human movement datasets in biomechanics and biomedical engineering research continuing to increase in both amount and complexity, adhering to the FAIR principles has become crucial for facilitating the open exchange of data. Practical checklists to verify the FAIRness of research data have been published [45, 46].

Figure 1. The FAIR Guiding Principles for the availability of data in publishing, based on [41].

Adherence to these FAIR principles forms a baseline recommendation of these guidelines when curating and preparing datasets for public release. However, the practical implementation of all subsections of these guidelines is inherently challenging, especially in light of the innate inhomogeneity of data in the human movement sciences. These society-endorsed recommendations therefore aim to address these challenges and support their resolution through recommendations specific to this field.

1.2. Data privacy in movement data

One of the key legal and ethical prerequisites of open-access data sharing specific to the field of human movement science is the fundamental need to respect an individual's right to data privacy. At this point, it is important to note that while we aim to provide a global perspective, we also acknowledge that country-specific regulations may vary [47]. Such variations clearly add a level of complexity and may not allow for full adherence to the FAIR principles, data privacy guidelines, and the following recommendations. Moreover, the regulatory landscape discussed herein draws on various legal frameworks, representing different but complementary perspectives on the issue of data privacy. It is therefore critical that scientists inform themselves of their own country's regulations as a minimal level of compliance. To maintain the impartiality of science, however, researchers are encouraged to commit to go beyond local requirements and fully fulfil ethical principles, even in daunting circumstances, for the benefit of science and scientists worldwide.

1.2.1. Personal vs. (sensitive) personally identifiable information

Any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual is considered *personal* [48]. Consequently, the data generated by experimental or clinical studies involving human research participants is, by definition, *personal information*, and is hence subject to specific regulations under most data protection legal frameworks (e.g. the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [48], often used as a reference due to its stringent regulation framework). Importantly, even personal data that have been de-identified, encrypted, or pseudonymised (see Sections 1.2.4 and 1.2.5) can still technically be used to identify a person and hence remain personal data. Higher-level descriptive and contextual data about an individual that could be used to trace their identity, such as name, date of birth, passport number, or biometric records, are considered *personally identifiable information* (PII). *Sensitive personally identifiable information* (SPII) such as racial or ethnic origin, genetic data, biometric data, or health data, is information that, if lost, compromised, or disclosed without authorisation, could result in substantial harm to an individual [49].

Even though experimental protocols in human movement research involving living participants will inherently generate personal data, this should not be considered a barrier to widespread data sharing in the field. However, researchers must make dedicated efforts to ensure that the quantity of *personally identifiable information* (PII) and especially of *sensitive personally identifiable information* (SPII) is minimised. Furthermore, the research community must be aware that while some forms of PII can be used in isolation to distinguish an individual's identity (such as their name, biometric data, or medical history), other forms of PII (such as ethnicity or country of origin) pose a risk only when considered in combination. Data protection strategies and risk stratification models should be put in place to safeguard a participant's identity, both when data are purposefully shared and as a precaution against potential data breaches (see Recs. B.5, B.6, C.2, C.3).

1.2.2. Data categorisation

While there is no globally recognised system in place for categorising data by sensitivity level, many proposed models have considerably overlapping, albeit inhomogeneous, nomenclature. Researchers are encouraged to check local policies when classifying the sensitivity level of data. While Table 1 presents generally accepted considerations for different data types, researchers should confirm by reviewing local regulations. Here, it is important to note that "damage" can include both *material harm* (e.g. financial loss/identity fraud) and/or *non-material harm* (e.g. distress, reputational harm, discrimination/harassment, loss of privacy/loss of control). Critically, harm is often context-dependent: the same dataset can expose the subject to different levels of risk depending on their circumstances (e.g. vulnerable populations, politically exposed persons, people in jurisdictions where certain attributes/conditions carry elevated personal risk, etc.). Consequently, infrastructures based on "secure-by-design" architectures are recommended (see Section 1.4, and Rec. C.3) for data sharing, as they can provide a viable framework for reducing the likelihood of data breaches.

Table 1. Categorisation and characteristics of different levels of personal data, including guiding considerations for data sharing.

Data type	Definition	Risk level	Examples	Consequences of unauthorised data breach for the individual or organisation	Considerations for the researcher/research institution to allow open data sharing
Anonymous data	Data for which identifiable characteristics were never collected.	None	E.g: "A man has a BMI of 35."	None	None
Aggregated data	Aggregation of anonymised / non-identifiable personal data.	None	E.g: "A group of 10 individuals has a mean body mass of 72 kg."	None	None
Anonymised / non-identifiable personal data	Personal data that has been processed such that associating it back to a specific individual is no longer possible, i.e. it is no longer identifiable. This process is called de-identification.	Low	E.g: "Unknown male participant, 50 years old, height 175 cm tall, 80 kg body mass, 74 cm step length." No names, dates of birth, or other identifying information.	No consequence since re-identification is either not possible or almost impossible. There are no restrictions on this type of data. Caveat: If the individual did not consent to data release, it is possible (although highly unlikely) for legal action to be taken.	Data can be freely shared in many jurisdictions. Anonymisation method must be documented, including a description of the residual risk of re-identification. Caveat: Without specific consent, data may not be shared. Ethical approval is strongly recommended to allow sharing of data, and may be mandatory in some jurisdictions.
Pseudonymised ("coded") personal data	Personal data that can still technically be attributed back to a given individual, but only with additional information.	Low	E.g: "Participant ZH05, Male, Born in 1976, 175 cm tall, 80 kg body mass." Medical images (CT, MRI, X-Ray, etc.) with embedded coded data also fall under this category (but may even be SPII in certain contexts)	No or inconsequential damage, as long as the pseudonymisation key remains safe.	Ethical approval is usually mandatory. General or specific informed consent is generally necessary to allow widespread data sharing (opt-out options are usually mandatory).
Directly identifiable personal data	Information that can uniquely identify an individual without additional data (e.g. even without the pseudonymisation key).	Moderate	E.g: Video data, photographs, etc. (Note: Biometric or PII if faces, tattoos, or other distinctive features are visible)	Possible damage to the individual. May qualify for legal action	Ethical approval is required. Specific consideration should be paid to written informed consent to allow widespread data sharing, and specifically for making directly identifiable personal data available (opt-in).
Personally identifiable information (PII)	Descriptive and contextual data about an individual that could uniquely identify the person.	Moderate	E.g: Name, date of birth, etc.	Moderate damage to an individual or organisation. Unauthorised release of this data qualifies for legal action.	Sharing should be avoided if possible and pursued only when ethical approval with specific written informed consent has been provided. The principle of data minimisation must be observed.
Sensitive personally identifiable information (SPII)	Information that if lost, compromised, or disclosed without authorisation, could result in substantial harm to an individual.	High	E.g: Medical history, clinical records, disability status, biometric data, medical images (CT, MRI, X-Ray, etc. in certain contexts)	Could result in substantial harm if lost, compromised, or disclosed without authorisation. Qualifies for legal action.	Should never be shared in uncoded form without ethical approval and explicit written informed consent. Should only be shared if thoroughly de-identified according to state-of-the-art techniques.

1.2.3. Informed consent

Obtaining written informed consent is a fundamental ethical and legal principle in healthcare, research, and other fields involving human participation. The specific formulations should be planned carefully before considering making data publicly available. While voluntary written informed consent is considered to be the basic minimum, categories of data usage extent include: **specific** (limited to the specific project, publishable only by the primary research team), **extended** (useable in other closely related work, but only within the same research area or purpose), or **unspecified** (general use of the data, with specific access conditions) [50]. While unspecified usage is clearly beneficial for data sharing, study participants might be hesitant to provide such broad and unspecified consent. One practical approach to mitigate participant reluctance is to employ a broad unspecified consent form that allows for unspecified further scientific usage of the data, but where the access request also requires elaboration on specific data and usage conditions.

A typical consent form would explicitly state that the data collected can be used for future research. Participants should additionally have a separate opt-in option for sharing specific data modalities (e.g. video, images, etc.), as well as another for allowing their de-identified data to be added to public repositories, while also retaining the right to withdraw their consent at any point in time without consequence. If a participant does not opt-in to these additional data sharing options, they do not necessarily become ineligible for the research study, where their data could still contribute to the aggregated findings. Importantly, researchers must be mindful of how they refer to data in these circumstances as it is inevitable that there will be private and public versions of the datasets. To avoid ambiguity and issues with the reproducibility of results, it is strongly recommended that researchers use clear nomenclature when referring to private and public versions of the same datasets.

It is clear that researchers must protect PII in a manner that complies with local data protection regulations. However, to make the sharing of human movement data available in a useful yet compliant manner, we also strongly recommend that only anonymous, fully anonymised, or pseudonymised data are shared. If SPII such as video footage, photography, or medical imaging are components that add critical value to the human movement data being shared, we strongly recommend that written informed consent, including specific approvals for use of data beyond the current research, is considered during the early stages of project planning (Rec. B.2).

To support practical adherence to these recommendations, we provide a guiding template of a consent form that can be adapted for use in applications to ethics committees and/or Institutional Review Boards (Supplementary Material, S1). While the wording will need to be adapted to include study-specific information and according to the appropriate jurisdiction, this consent form can be used to ensure that researchers meet the minimum requirements for enabling open sharing of their data.

1.2.4. Anonymisation vs. pseudonymisation

Anonymisation and *pseudonymisation* are fundamentally different. *Anonymisation* involves processing personal data to the extent that associating it back to a specific individual is no longer possible, i.e. such that the data is no longer *identifiable* (see also Sections 1.2.1, 1.2.2, and Table 1). This could involve strategic deletions in metadata, or aggregation of data into

categories. Importantly, data that has been fully anonymised is technically no longer *personal data* and hence usually falls outside the scope of data protection laws [51]. As a result, where appropriate ethical approvals are in place, such data can be shared freely without impairment. Critically, anonymised data can no longer be linked to additional data of the same participant, and the data's authenticity and correctness can no longer be verified.

With *pseudonymisation*, attribution of personal data back to a given individual is technically possible, but only with additional information (such as an alphanumeric key or other unique identifier) that must be stored separately according to local data protection regulation, and to which access must be strictly managed to reduce the risk of identifiability [51]. While pseudonymisation reduces data privacy risks, the data remain personal data and therefore *do* fall within the scope of most data protection legal frameworks (e.g. EU's GDPR, UK's DPA, etc.) [52]. It is important to note that such data are not prohibited from being shared, provided ethical and legal conditions are met.

1.2.5. Encryption vs. encoding

Strictly speaking, the terms *data encryption* and *data encoding* are not interchangeable. *Encryption* relies on using a secret key to transform information, hence reducing security risks and maintaining confidentiality [51]. Although the data is rendered uninterpretable to those without access to the secret key, the original information is still accessible to those with the key, as they can use it to reverse the encryption process, i.e. *decryption*. Encryption can therefore be used as a valuable tool for pseudonymisation; for example, by using it to replace an individual's name with a random, unique alphanumeric code. While encryption is focused on ensuring data *security*, *encoding* is instead related to data *usability* [53]. *Encoding* deals with the way data is represented, e.g. as plain text or binary data, or in a structured file format such as CSV, XML, JSON, etc. [53-55]. Unlike with encryption, the algorithms or schemes used for data encoding are publicly available (e.g. ASCII, Unicode, URL, Base64, etc.); transforming the data to a different format does not improve security but rather allows it to be read by different systems [55].

1.2.6. Identifiability of movement data

Repetitive movement patterns, such as walking, have long been acknowledged as behavioural biometrics [56, 57]. The ubiquity of monitoring systems such as video surveillance has allowed exploitative efforts to leverage gait patterns for the automated recognition of individuals [58]. In fact, recent research combining multiple datasets using deep learning approaches has already achieved ~90% re-identification accuracy [59]. Consequently, legitimate concerns about the re-identifiability of previously de-identified human movement data have now been raised. With further technical advances in artificial intelligence and machine learning, as well as increased amounts and specificity of data, re-identification accuracy will only rise. From a legal perspective, access to shared movement data should therefore only be provided after the safeguard of a signed agreement, committing users not to attempt re-identification of movement datasets (Rec. D.4).

1.2.7. Data accessibility

While we appreciate that citizen science efforts promote public engagement within specific fields, these activities do not typically deal with *personally identifiable* information (see Section 2.2.1). In human movement sciences, we recognise that the sensitive nature of such data should limit the scope of its accessibility. To uphold data protection standards, we therefore

recommend that the human movement sciences community ensures appropriate control with respect to data access (Rec. C.2). Building on examples from genomics, where admission to repositories is regulated through a process of authentication [60], we recommend that data access is safeguarded and only granted once the administrative organisation has confirmed a user's credentials, including agreement to comply with local security, ethical, and legal standards. Interestingly, this approach shifts access responsibility towards the society or organisation to act as gatekeeper to safeguard the interests of the study participants in the context of their data becoming widely available.

1.3. Licences for data sharing

Although often overlooked, licensing is an important part of data sharing and should be carefully considered whenever data is published. Here, the role and applicability of licensing will critically depend upon the type and structure of data being shared. A key challenge facing the scientific community in this context is that personal data ownership does not fit within the traditional legal framework of property ownership [61], since data protection regulations stipulate that individuals maintain the right to consent, access, correct, and delete their data even if a third-party collects, possesses, or controls it. As such, personal data cannot be copyrighted [62], but conclusions from these data, including graphs, figures, research papers, etc., can. In other words, a researcher does not *own* a participant's raw data just because they collected it; instead, written informed consent can grant them a right to *use* and *share* it, but also obliges them to safeguard it.

In the context of open science, licensing plays a crucial role, especially as researchers sharing datasets may inadvertently restrict the extent to which their datasets can be legally used by (and therefore be of value to) others by neglecting to clearly associate a license to their work. Licensing empowers both the author of a curated dataset (as opposed to the raw data itself) as well as any potential users, by delineating *who* can re-use the dataset, *how* the dataset can be used, and for what *purposes*. Dataset controllers (i.e. individuals or organisations that are responsible for dataset processing, usage, and compliance [63]) benefit from licensing as it ensures proper attribution, protects their rights as curators, and grants them control over derivatives of their work. Conversely, users of a dataset benefit from having an explicit framework to guide their use of the dataset in a legally compliant manner.

A license can only be granted by whomever owns copyright over the work, which is generally the creator [64]. While copyright protects original creative works [65], raw factual data (such as measurements or recordings) typically have limited copyright protection, as facts themselves are not copyrightable [66]. However, compiled databases may allow copyright protection based on their curation and arrangement [67]. For research involving personal data, the right to share data is specifically derived from a combination of informed consent from the study participant, ethical approval, and compliance with data protection regulations, rather than from copyright or ownership rights alone. Notably, licensing and copyright will apply specifically to the dataset's *structure*, rather than the individual raw data elements contained within [63]. Researchers must ensure that any licensing applied to datasets is consistent with the consent obtained and applicable data protection laws, as participants retain privacy rights over their personal information even when it is shared. Before licensing data, researchers should therefore assess: 1) whether they hold copyright over the dataset as a compilation, 2) whether they have obtained appropriate consent and ethical approval for the intended sharing, 3) whether their employer or institution holds rights to the work (e.g. employers may often own

the copyright to work created by their employees [64]), and 4) whether their funding institution mandates specific licensing requirements. Each researcher should therefore confirm their own specific situation before proceeding with data sharing, keeping in mind that a permissive license does not override data protection requirements or negate any of the participants' rights.

Although different licensing frameworks exist, the most widely used is provided by the international nonprofit Creative Commons (CC) organisation (Figure 2), presenting a valuable licensing framework for creators and academics, with free-to-use CC licenses for granting copyright permissions and ensuring proper attribution. The organisation offers a convenient "License Chooser" [68] that supports users in selecting an appropriate license: By Attribution (BY) should be selected to ensure appropriate credit is attributed to the authors; Non-Commercial (NC) to permit only non-commercial applications; No Derivatives (ND) in cases where derivatives or adaptations are not authorised; and Share Alike (SA) wherever adaptations should be re-shared under the same CC license (even though this licensing model is unlikely in the framework of data sharing). Importantly, CC licensing is not revocable, and hence creators should carefully consider their chosen license at initial publication (Rec D1-D2). Moreover, Creative Commons explicitly recommends against using their licenses for software, and instead endorses opting for a dedicated free "open-source" license wherever possible, such as the Free Software Foundation's GNU General Public License [69].

Creative Commons Licenses		COPY & PUBLISH	ATTRIBUTION REQUIRED	COMMERCIAL USE	MODIFY & ADAPT	CHANGE LICENSE
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You can redistribute.	You have to attribute the original.	You can use the work commercially.	You can modify & adapt the original.	You can choose license type for adaptations.

Figure 2. Creative Commons Licenses at a Glance (Adapted from original: "How to Attribute Creative Commons Photos", licensed as CC BY-SA 3.0 in <https://foter.com/blog/how-to-attribute-creative-commons-photos/>).

1.3.1. Data attribution

When mandated by a license, data attribution serves as both a legal requirement and ethical imperative in research data sharing, ensuring that original dataset creators receive proper credit when their work is reused. In open data contexts, attribution is formally mandated through licenses such as Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) or Open Data Commons Attribution License (ODC-By). For personal data governed by frameworks like the GDPR, attribution practices must critically operate alongside stringent privacy protection regulations, requiring researchers to balance proper crediting of data sources with robust de-identification measures, access controls, and informed consent mechanisms. The integration of clear attribution practices, typically specified through metadata, licenses, and permanent identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), enable researchers to track provenance and identify when datasets have been reused or shared across multiple platforms. Proper attribution thus ensures accountability even throughout distributed data ecosystems such as federated open sharing models, where this tracking ability is particularly valuable as raw data remain at the contributing source and only analysis results, whether aggregated statistics, harmonised datasets, or individual-level findings, are released (see Section 1.4).

Ultimately, comprehensive data attribution frameworks serve multiple purposes: protecting the intellectual contributions of dataset creators in open sharing contexts, maintaining accountability and transparency in the handling of personal data, enabling proper tracking and citation, avoiding duplication of datasets, and fostering trust in research ecosystems. These frameworks thus ensure compliance with legal obligations, uphold ethical standards, and promote a culture where both dataset creators and research participants are appropriately recognised and protected throughout the data lifecycle.

1.4. Data storage infrastructure

Data storage is subject not only to legal but also ethical considerations, including storage duration, personalised access rights, encryption, and incident reporting. Data storage infrastructure models to provide such conditions for open-access sharing can be broadly classified as either centralised or federated [70, 71]. In a centralised model, data from multiple sources are aggregated onto a single server that users can access directly. While this approach offers theoretical advantages such as enhanced data consistency and efficiency, such models require all data to comply with the storage regulations of the host jurisdiction [72]. This poses significant challenges for human movement data acquired by research groups worldwide, as specific legal restrictions in many countries prohibit offshore data storage. Federated models address these limitations by using a *hub-and-spoke* architecture that maintains centralised governance while keeping data decentralised, i.e. housed on servers at each researcher's institution. By allowing data to remain under local institutional control, federated systems therefore overcome certain regulatory hurdles that would otherwise restrict international data sharing, while also providing an additional layer of security towards mitigating risks associated with data breaches. Specifically, federated implementations can be designed to output aggregated results with curator-level analysis (also presenting opportunities to leverage shared analysis tools), providing an additional layer of privacy protection, maintaining data integrity, and ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.

The growing need to access SPII for research purposes, coupled with heightened awareness of data breach risks, has led to the development of so-called *Trusted Research*

Environments (TREs) [73]. A TRE is a secure, administered computing environment, typically hosted on cloud platforms such as Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services, or Google Cloud, that enables researchers to access shared data safely and securely [74]. TREs can additionally provide substantial computation capabilities to create workflows where researchers can access SII data, perform custom analyses, and export derived datasets while maintaining data integrity. While TREs offer unprecedented opportunities as training environments for machine learning models [75] based on large, aggregated datasets, their utility extends far beyond such applications. TREs could be well-suited to the diverse analytical approaches common in biomechanics and human movement research, including kinematic analysis, inverse dynamics, musculoskeletal modelling, and statistical comparisons of movement patterns. For additional considerations on data localisation vs. sovereignty, the decentralised vs. centralised aspects of federated architectures, and the design of a step-by-step platform structure to guide researchers through practical compliance, see Supplementary Material S2.

2. Metadata Reporting

2.1. General data descriptors

Metadata provide descriptive characteristics that convey information about datasets, making them an essential prerequisite for compliance with the FAIR principles. The value of comprehensive metadata documentation cannot be overstated: detailed metadata enable researchers to efficiently identify datasets relevant to their specific research questions, understand the context and limitations of the collected data, and determine whether a dataset's characteristics align with the researcher's own analytical needs.

The more thoroughly metadata are documented, the more accessible and valuable the datasets become to the wider research community, hence facilitating reuse, cross-study comparisons, and meta-analyses that advance our collective understanding in the human movement sciences. However, overly prescriptive metadata requirements risk creating substantial barriers to data sharing, burdening the contributors with excessive time, resource, and financial commitments. Striking an appropriate balance is therefore essential: insufficient metadata renders datasets difficult to properly utilise, while overly burdensome documentation requirements may discourage researchers from sharing valuable data. While the Fair Information Practice Principles (FIPP) advocate for minimisation of the amount of identifiable data [76], open data sharing practices dictate that metadata is provided as comprehensively as ethically and legally permissible [41, 77]. By committing to open sharing principles that protect participant privacy, the research community has an initial basis to guide consensus-based thresholds for minimally appropriate levels of documentation that balance usability with feasibility.

While robust metadata frameworks have been established in fields such as genomics [78], neuroimaging [79], and bioimaging [80], comparable standardised schemes for documenting human movement data remain insufficiently mature for widespread adoption. We therefore strongly endorse concerted community efforts, such as consensus-building through Delphi studies or similar collaborative approaches [37], to develop, validate, and implement metadata standards based on unified terminology that comprehensively capture and describe specific characteristics (Table 2). Such standardisation efforts must address the inherent

complexity of human movement data, including diverse measurement modalities (marker-based optical systems, IMUs, markerless video, etc.), heterogeneous study populations spanning multiple pathologies and interventions, and longitudinal designs with variable follow-up timepoints. Furthermore, the increasingly multimodal nature of human movement research, integrating functional kinematics with imaging, electromyography, force measurements, and clinical assessments, demands careful structural consideration to ensure interoperability and future compatibility as technologies and analytical methods evolve. Specifically, as a key subset of human movement science data, we recommend that metadata for reporting joint kinematics addresses as many of the following aspects as possible:

Table 2. Proposed metadata descriptors for documenting kinematic data in human movement datasets.

Descriptor	Key Characteristics	Specific Considerations	
Ethics & Accessibility	Consent & approval	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethical review approval documented (institution and ID) Written informed consent obtained Extent of consent specified (specific use, extended, unspecified) 	
	Privacy protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appropriate pseudonymisation/anonymisation Removal of identifying information 	
	Licensing & reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Author, institution, contact details Clear license specified (e.g. CC-BY, CC-BY-ND) including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terms of use Attribution requirements 	
Documentation & Metadata	Experimental protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protocol documentation enabling reproducibility Study design Task instructions to participant and activity standardisation procedures Environmental conditions (lab vs. field, surface type, clothing and shoe type, etc.) Coordinate system definitions (global and local) Reference pose/calibration procedures 	
	Sensor/marker placement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anatomical landmark definitions Placement protocols Visual documentation (diagrams, photos) where applicable 	
	Event labelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gait event definitions and labelling procedure Laterality (left vs. right) 	
	Unusual observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation of unexpected events during collection Participant-specific notes or deviations from protocol Technical issues or anomalies reported 	
	Temporal relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date/year of data collection Technology generation (e.g. marker-based systems from different eras) Contextual factors 	
	Coverage & Scope	Population representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demographics (age, sex, ethnicity, BMI, height, limb dominance, etc.) Health status, including specific pathology Activity level, clinical outcomes, functional scores, etc. Sample size and distribution across subgroups
		Temporal extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Duration of data collection per session Number of trials per participant Time period over which data were collected
Related datasets		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to associated data 	
Signal Processing	Sampling parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sampling frequency Anti-aliasing procedures 	
	Filtering & smoothing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smoothing methods Unsmoothed data availability Filter specifications (type, cutoff frequencies, order) 	
	Gap-filling procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methods used for interpolation (linear, polynomial, spline, etc.) and/or gap-filling 	
	Data exclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outlier detection methods 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for data exclusion
	Processing pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software, version • Processing workflow from raw to processed data • Openly available code/algorithms • Version control for processing tools

Where applicable, metadata fields should be populated using established coding standards (e.g. SNOMED CT for clinical terms, LOINC for observation identifiers, ISO 80000 for units of measurement) to maximise machine readability and cross-domain interoperability. Importantly, unavailable fields should be clearly marked to distinguish genuine information absence from incomplete reporting. Since this non-exhaustive list may seem daunting, we recommend that practical implementation of such metadata frameworks be structured hierarchically in order to ensure that the data is concise, as well as machine-, and ideally, human-readable.

2.2. Data quality

Large collections of kinematic data will inherently encompass a spectrum of data qualities and fidelities, spanning dimensions such as accuracy, precision, and temporal or spatial resolution. Importantly, poorly collected or error-ridden data (e.g. inadequate equipment calibration, excessive gaps in marker trajectories, incorrect event detection, etc.) should at a minimum be appropriately flagged (e.g. through automated testing) and possibly excluded where appropriate. Notably, however, quality is determined by the extent to which data can fulfil its intended purpose. While research often prioritises the highest accuracy attainable, lower resolution or accuracy does not inherently diminish a dataset's value; rather, it offers different analytical opportunities depending on the research question at hand. For instance, while high-precision dual-plane moving fluoroscopy may be essential for detailed articular joint kinematic analyses [81], lower-resolution marker-based or markerless approaches offer distinct advantages for other applications: they are non-invasive, substantially more scalable, and often better suited for population-level hypothesis generation or widespread clinical screening efforts [82-84]. Datasets from different sources can therefore be better suited to address distinct research questions, making accurate characterisation of data quality dimensions essential for researchers to find and appropriately utilise shared data.

To facilitate the characterisation of data quality, as well as the searchability of shared datasets to answer a given research question, we strongly recommend that quality metrics accompany shared kinematic datasets (e.g. Table 3). Importantly, this concept of quality reporting is not designed to judge the value of datasets. Instead, the goal is to provide objective *descriptive* characterisation of data attributes (i.e. reporting what the data *are*) rather than *prescriptive* assessments of dataset merit (i.e. appraising the data's value based on a normative notion of what the data *should be*). This approach is not designed to exclude datasets or discourage data sharing by imposing restrictive quality thresholds, but rather to ensure transparency, enabling end-users to evaluate whether a particular dataset's characteristics align with their own specific research objectives. One such example might be the use of shared data for studies or hypothesis generation in e.g. fall risk assessment based on whole body movement characteristics in real-world settings, where sub-mm quantification of single joint articular kinematics will not be able to provide ecologically valid risk indicators. While comprehensive metadata reporting may be labour-intensive, failing to report quality descriptors could fundamentally limit data discoverability and reusability, ultimately undermining the value of open data sharing.

Table 3. Examples of quality descriptors (non-exhaustive).

Descriptor	Key Characteristics	Specific Considerations
Measurement Quality	Sensor resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resolution of measurement systems (spatial and temporal) • Uncertainty quantification (experimental or manufacturer specifications, results of calibration procedure) • Noise level quantification (e.g. soft-tissue artefacts)
	Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison against gold standard systems (e.g. fluoroscopy) • Ground truth availability for accuracy assessment • Examiner expertise/experience • Assessments of reproducibility, repeatability, and reliability
Completeness	Missing data documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of missing data points per trial (e.g. occluded markers per frame) • Missing trials per participant • Missing modalities per participant • Participant dropouts from the study • Documentation of equipment failures or collection issues

Such a matrix should be validated through Delphi type studies and may well vary according to the specifics of each study.

2.3. File format considerations

The choice of file format is a fundamental yet frequently overlooked consideration that directly impacts the findability, interoperability, and long-term reusability of shared human movement datasets. File formats govern how data are structured, encoded, and read by different software environments, and consequently determine the ease with which datasets can be exchanged, integrated, and preserved across institutions and over time. In the human movement sciences, data are commonly stored in a wide variety of proprietary (e.g. manufacturer-specific binary formats tied to particular motion capture systems) and open formats (e.g. CSV, C3D, JSON, HDF5), each presenting distinct trade-offs between the richness of embedded metadata, cross-platform compatibility, human readability, and storage efficiency.

Proprietary formats, while often optimised for specific acquisition systems, risk creating vendor lock-in and may become inaccessible as software evolves or licences expire, thereby threatening the long-term preservation and reproducibility of shared datasets. Open, well documented, and widely supported formats that are both forward- and backward-compatible should therefore be strongly preferred for data dissemination, as they lower barriers to access and reduce dependency on specific commercial software ecosystems. Where proprietary formats are unavoidable, for instance, when raw acquisition data must be retained to ensure full traceability of the processing pipeline, researchers are encouraged to additionally provide data in at least one open, non-proprietary format. Furthermore, selected file formats should ideally be capable of embedding or accompanying structured metadata (see Section 2.1), such that descriptive information travels with the data rather than being stored in separate, easily dissociated files. Community convergence towards a minimal set of recommended file formats, informed by ongoing standardisation efforts (e.g. Motion-BIDS [36], C3D), would substantially enhance interoperability and reduce the friction associated with cross-institutional data harmonisation and sharing, while clearly distinguishing between motion capture raw data, processed biomechanical data, and derived summary outcomes intended for statistical analysis.

In this regard, the Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5) [85, 86] merits particular attention as a candidate for standardised data exchange in the human movement sciences. Already widely adopted across scientific disciplines and also employed by motion analysis software providers (e.g. export feature in the AnyBody Technology A/S product, or project data

storage in Moveck Solution Inc. products), HDF5 offers a self-describing, platform-independent, and highly scalable architecture capable of accommodating the large, heterogeneous datasets typical of biomechanical research. Critically, HDF5 functions as a container format; it provides a flexible hierarchical structure of groups and datasets analogous to a file system, but does not inherently prescribe how domain-specific content should be organised within that structure. The adoption of HDF5 as a data sharing format for the human movement sciences therefore necessitates e.g. the concurrent development of well-defined content specifications that address the full breadth of requirements for both motion capture and motion analysis data, including raw sensor signals, processed kinematics and kinetics, model parameters, event annotations, and associated metadata. These content specifications should be developed through broad community consensus, ensuring compatibility with the diverse acquisition modalities, processing pipelines, and analytical workflows present across the field, while remaining extensible to accommodate future technological developments. Ultimately, thoughtful file format selection at the point of data collection and curation is a prerequisite for achieving the FAIR principles in practice, and should be considered an integral component of any data sharing plan (Rec. B.4).

3. Best Practices and Recommendations for Practical Implementation

It is critical to acknowledge that appropriate adherence to legal and ethical frameworks for the global sharing of human movement data presents considerable challenges. The complexity of navigating diverse, country-specific regulations can make the process appear overwhelming and resource-intensive. However, the potential benefits of well-structured and standardised recommendations for data sharing to the research community are substantial towards the advancement of science and improved patient treatment. Therefore, in an effort to promote Open Data practices and support researchers in overcoming these barriers, we propose the following set of practical, implementable recommendations (Supplementary Material, S3) designed to facilitate compliance but with a reasonable time and effort investment.

A. General Recommendations for Researchers

1. Adhere to the strictest international and national regulations.

Legal standards are dynamic, and researchers should verify compliance with the regulations applicable to their jurisdiction. If possible, researchers should adhere to the strictest current legal frameworks, such that data sharing becomes possible across countries.

2. Adhere to established ethical principles.

Contact your local ethics committees and/or institutional review boards (IRBs) at an early timepoint before commencing a study to ensure compliance of data sharing with context-specific ethical standards.

3. Commit to the FAIR principles as a foundation for responsible data sharing.

Ensure that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) to support robust and reproducible research that aligns with the principles of Open Data.

B. Data Collection and Data Sharing for Researchers

1. Obtain ethical approval before initiating any data collection.

Ethical approval should be granted by a recognised competent ethics authority (e.g. institutional review board and/or governmental ethics committee).

2. Integrate provisions for obtaining written informed consent from participants early in the study planning stage.

Early planning of informed consent ensures that the necessary measures to protect the participants' rights are an integral feature of the study design.

3. Obtain written informed consent that explicitly permits data sharing.

The participants' rights – including the right to refuse data sharing or withdraw their consent and have their data excluded from future use, at any time, without penalty, and without having to provide an explanation – should be respected at all times and prioritised over data sharing. Where possible, consent should then be sufficiently broad to allow for future, unspecified scientific use of the data.

4. Use data harmonisation tools and standardised terminologies to ensure consistency and reproducibility across datasets.

Beyond aligning data and file formats, harmonisation ensures that data from different sources can be meaningfully aggregated, compared, and interpreted. This includes using methodological frameworks that account for variability in data acquisition, processing, and representation.

5. Adhere to the principle of data minimisation when collecting sensitive personal information.

Only sensitive personal information that is ethically approved and directly relevant for the research objectives should be collected. This reduces risks of violating the participants' rights, supports ethical compliance, and aligns with many of the stricter data protection regulations (e.g. GDPR).

6. Share only anonymous, anonymised, or pseudonymised data.

To protect participant privacy, shared datasets must not contain directly identifiable information. Where full anonymisation is not feasible, pseudonymisation techniques should be implemented, and access to keys should be appropriately protected.

7. Prioritise transparency and reproducibility in data collection, processing, and analysis.

Although the publication of scientific manuscripts in a peer-reviewed journal will often provide most methodological details, additional documentation accompanying shared datasets is highly encouraged to ensure sufficient details for reproducibility are reported (e.g. exact processing workflows from raw data to joint kinematics and kinetics).

8. Ensure financially sustainable models for data sharing.

Ensure financial sustainability as a pre-requisite for long-term maintenance and preservation of data sharing frameworks, possibly acquiring support through sponsorship or long-term grants. However, strive to ensure data remains accessible to academia free of charge.

C. Data Collection and Data Sharing for Institutions

1. Provide safe and secure infrastructure that meets legal requirements to support data sharing.

Support researchers by providing access to data servers or platforms that meet legal requirements to facilitate data sharing.

2. Ensure data is stored and transferred securely, in accordance with legal requirements.

Storage and transfer systems must ensure confidentiality, integrity, and availability. This includes using encrypted servers, implementing access controls, logging user activity to support audit trails, and complying with relevant data protection regulations. Long-term storage plans should consider data retention periods, sustainable data formats, and secure deletion protocols.

3. Data should remain at the site of origin and be accessed only through secure, federated systems.

Federated data sharing allows data to remain within its original institution while enabling access for analysis through trusted research environments (TREs). This approach enhances privacy, supports compliance with local regulations, and facilitates collaborative research without compromising data sovereignty.

4. Promote equality and inclusivity in data access.

Strive to provide equal access to data. This involves ensuring that data sharing practices do not reinforce existing disparities in data access (e.g. due to paywalls, etc.).

D. Data Licensing for Researchers

- 1. Include only data that has been originally collected within the own research group when contributing to a trusted research environment or repository.**
To avoid intellectual property conflicts, researchers should only license and share datasets for which they can guarantee the validity, and for which they hold the rights. Data obtained from external sources should not be uploaded unless explicit permission has been granted and the upload is properly documented.
- 2. Explicitly associate a license to datasets to clarify permitted uses.**
Attaching a clear, standardised license (e.g. Creative Commons Attribution, CC BY) communicates the terms under which data can be reused, adapted, and/or redistributed. In general, CC BY should be used if possible, with the addition of NC to restrict commercial use if necessary.
- 3. Assign a persistent, unique identifier (e.g. DOI) to each dataset.**
Assign a unique identifier in order to align with the FAIR principles, facilitate proper attribution, and enhance visibility and impact of the dataset.
- 4. Avoid data re-identification.**
Commit to not re-identifying de-identified data as part of a responsible data usage agreement.

E. Metadata for Researchers

- 1. Include descriptive and standardised metadata at the time of data collection.**
Inclusion of descriptive metadata at the time of data collection supports future integration and reuse, and avoids mislabelling. Where applicable, researchers should adopt or align with established terminology and coding standards from adjacent domains.
- 2. Provide a realistic but inclusive set of metadata with every dataset.**
Metadata requirements should be sufficiently detailed to support data harmonisation and re-use, but not so exhaustive as to impede data sharing.
- 3. Use a hierarchical metadata structure to organise key information.**
A layered approach (including required and optional fields) is recommended to allow contributors to report essential information without being overwhelmed. Metadata should cover access and governance (e.g. ethical approval ID, license type, data sensitivity), technical details (e.g. data capture methods, data quality metrics), and cohort/study characteristics (e.g. demographics, anthropometry, study design, pathology). A streamlined format that allows data to be easily searched is critical.
- 4. Ensure participant metadata is as specific and comprehensive as possible, while protecting participants' privacy.**
If possible, participant metadata should avoid directly identifiable information (e.g. instead of date of birth, consider age at time of measurement, age group, or year of birth).

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Competing Interests

A.O.-V. receives research funding from Aesculap AG and is listed as a co-inventor on a pending patent application filed by Aesculap AG (DE102022125697A1). A.S. is an employee of Aesculap AG and is also listed as a co-inventor on the same pending patent application. K.N.V.'s research is supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation and Krebsforschung Schweiz, unrelated to this work. K.N.V. is a member of the European Society of Medical Oncology (ESMO) Cancer Medicines Committee. A.B. is the CEO and founder of Moveck Solution Inc. E.T. is a director of Operdi Limited. D.M. is the Digital Systems Lead of NEXUS Personalized Health Technologies at ETH Zurich. S.D. has co-founded multiple health technology companies, including Musculographics (now Motion Analysis Corp), Surgical Graphics (acquired by Medtronic), and Cala Health. All other authors declare no competing interests.

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